

Syntheses of Some Terpenoids via Nickel Tetracarbonyl Induced Cyclisation*

O. P. VIG

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

ON this occasion I convey my sincere thanks to the Indian Chemical Society for giving me this opportunity to deliver the Acharya J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture. Acharya Ghosh's contribution to the cause of science and education in India stands out as a lighthouse for the younger generation of scientists and will continue to inspire them in their pursuit for better understanding of the world of science.

Few subjects have perhaps made greater progress within the last decade than organic synthesis involving organo-metallic reagents. Partly because of this reason I have chosen for to-day's talk an aspect of organo-metallic chemistry which involves π -allyl nickel intermediates and their applications in the field of terpenoids.

Carbon-Carbon bond formation via π -allyl nickel complex

Allyl system $\xrightarrow{\text{Ni(CO)}_4}$ (π -allylnickel complex)

Intermolecular coupling

Scheme 1

The π -nickel complexes shown in Scheme 1 are formed in good yields by the reaction of a variety of allyl bromides with an excess of Ni(CO)_4 in dry benzene at 50° under inert atmosphere¹. These complexes are relatively inert towards alkyl halides in hydrocarbon or ether type solvents². In polar, co-ordinating media, viz., DMF, N-methyl pyrrolidine, hexamethyl phosphoramide etc., a facile reaction occurs between the complex and a

wide variety of organic halides including vinyl and aryl halides to furnish coupled products in high yields.

It may be pointed out here that the treatment of π -complexes with dissimilar allyl halides can result in an exchange reaction giving rise to a new π -nickel allyl complex with the resultant formation of a mixture of coupled products. If the allyl group in the allyl halide and π -nickel complex is the same, the reaction is then normal.

Intramolecular coupling :

An intramolecular version of this reaction has been usefully extended to the synthesis of cyclic 1,5-diene systems using appropriate *bis*-allylic halides and employing high dilution technique to inhibit the intermolecular reaction³. The cyclic 1,5-diene moieties have invariably *trans-trans* geometry irrespective of the stereochemistry of the olefinic linkages in the starting *bis*-allylic halides. Application of this technique has been made in achieving the syntheses of naturally occurring 12, 14 and 18 membered ring compounds including humulene, casbene, cembrene and macrolides in yields ranging from 60-80%.

Scheme 2

* Acharya J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture (1979) delivered under the auspices of Indian Chemical Society on 27th December 1981 at Madras.

As shown in Scheme 2, when the value of $n=2$ or 4 in the acyclic bis-allylic halides, the formation of 6-membered ring is favoured relative to 8 or 10 membered rings. The cyclic intermediate, 1,5-diene, formed is believed to undergo Cope's rearrangement resulting in the formation of substituted 6-membered rings.

In the first case the formation of 4-vinyl cyclohexene took place preferentially to 8-membered ring and where $n=4$, the product consisted entirely of a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-1,2-divinyl cyclohexene. This selective course of the reaction has been exploited in designing a synthetic route to naturally occurring monocyclic sesquiterpene, elemenes.

Another gratifying aspect of this coupling reaction is the compatibility of the presence of an array of additional functional groups in the starting allylic halides, such as isolated double bonds, keto or ester groups, which we have also amply demonstrated in some of the syntheses of the naturally occurring terpenoids, I am going to discuss.

Synthesis of (\pm) cubitene, a 12-membered monocyclic diterpene :

A novel irregular 12-membered monocyclic diterpene hydrocarbon, cubitene, was recently isolated as a major constituent of the defensive secretions released from the frontal glands of soldiers of East-African termite *Cubitermes umratus* Williams⁵. On the basis of spectral studies, chemical reactions and X-ray diffraction data, it was shown to be (8*S*, 10*R*)-1,5-dimethyl-8,10-bis(isopropenyl)cyclododeca-1(*E*),5(*E*)-diene.

The salient features of the structure are the presence of a 12-membered monocyclic ring with two isopropenyl substituents and two triply substituted olefinic bonds in the form of 1,5-diene unit in the macrocyclic ring.

The two *E*-trisubstituted double bonds which are part of the 1,5-diene moiety of cubitene have been created by nickelcarbonyl coupling reaction. This coupling reaction has been found to give mixtures of double bond isomers regardless of the homogeneity of the precursors when triply substituted double bonds are involved. Therefore, the stereochemistry of these two double bonds in cubitene precursors was not an important consideration.

The reaction sequence employed for the synthesis is shown in Scheme 3.

The starting material for the synthesis was the easily available methylheptenone ketal (I) which was subjected to selenium dioxide oxidation to the allylic alcohol (II) which was converted into the corresponding vinyl ether (III) through mercuric acetate catalysed transesterification with ethylvinyl ether. Claisen rearrangement of this vinyl ether under nitrogen atmosphere furnished the ketal aldehyde (IV) with one isopropenyl substituent at

Scheme 3

the C-3 position. Modified Wittig reaction of ethyl α -diethyl phosphonopropionate in diglyme on this ketal aldehyde gave ethyl 8-ethylenedioxy-5-isopropenyl-2-methyl non-2-enoate (V) which was found to be predominantly an *E*-isomer as indicated by its pmr analysis (*E* : *Z* :: 4 : 1).

No attempt was, however, made to separate the two isomers because both the isomers were expected to lead to the same aldehyde after reduction, vinyl etherification and Claisen rearrangement.

On LAH reduction in dry benzene at 60° this conjugated ester gave the carbinol (VI) which on usual equilibration with excess of ethyl vinyl ether provided 8,8-ethylenedioxy-5-isopropenyl-2-methyl-1-vinyloxy-non-2-ene (VII), which after purification was submitted to Claisen rearrangement under nitrogen atmosphere at 190-95° for 30 min when it generated the olefinic aldehyde (VIII) as a pleasant smelling liquid. This was subjected to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl α -diethylphosphonopropionate to afford the conjugated ester (IX). Confirmation of the *E* stereochemistry of conjugated ester was obtained from its pmr spectrum which showed C₈ proton at δ 6.7.

VIG : SYNTHESIS OF SOME TERPENOIDS VIA NICKEL TETRACARBONYL INDUCED CYCLISATION

The compound was deketalised with PTS in acetone-water at room temperature to give ethyl 5,7-bis(isopropenyl)-2-methyl-10-oxo-2(E)-undecanoate (X). Modified Wittig reaction on this keto-ester with ethyl-diethylphosphonoacetate under the usual reaction conditions yielded a stereoisomeric mixture of (E, E) and (E, Z)-diesters (XI) (6 : 1), diethyl 2,6-dimethyl-5,7-bis(isopropenyl) dodeca-2,10-dien-1,12-dioate in which the (E, E) isomer was predominant as indicated by pmr spectrum. No attempt was made to separate the isomers. As has been stated earlier, whatever be the nature of olefinic linkages in the starting allylic halides, the composition of the isomers in the cyclised product remains the same. Reduction of this diester with LAH in dry benzene gave the diol (XII) as a viscous liquid which was converted into the corresponding dibromide (XIII). The labile allylic dibromide was reacted with nickel tetracarbonyl in DMF at 47-50° under nitrogen atmosphere. The cyclisation product showed two distinct spots (R_f 0.93, 0.76) on tlc analysis, using *n*-hexane as the solvent system, indicating the presence of two components. The two components were separated by column chromatography over $AgNO_3$ impregnated silica gel. The less polar major component (R_f 0.93) was obtained in 10% yield and its identity was established by comparison of its spectral data with those reported for natural cubitene. The second product (R_f 0.76; 3% yield) appeared to be a dimer of cubitene as revealed by its pmr spectrum which had very close resemblance with that of cubitene, except the allylic methyl signals which in the case of the dimer appeared at δ 1.62. The high resolution mass spectrum of this dimer showed a molecular ion (M^+) at m/e 544.5 corresponding to the molecular formula $C_{40}H_{84}$ of the dimer. Thus the dimer could be assigned the cyclic structure shown below :

This structure of the dimer was supported by its ir and nmr data also.

The possibility of acyclic dimer Xvc was ruled out on the basis of pmr and mass spectral analysis. For acyclic components vinyl methyl H 30 and M^+ at m/e 546.5.

A new synthesis of humulene :

Humulene, a monocyclic sesquiterpenic hydrocarbon has been isolated from the oil of hops, *Humulus lupulus* Linn. and the essential oil of wild ginger, *Zinziber zerumbat*⁶. As a result of the comprehensive chemical, spectroscopic and X-ray crystallographic studies, it has been assigned the structure 2,6,6,9-tetramethylcycloundeca-1,4,8-triene. Structural features of the humulene molecule are presence of 11-membered ring with a gem dimethyl substituent, two *trans* triply substituted double bonds in the form of 1,5-diene unit in the macrocyclic ring and a doubly substituted *trans* double bond between C_4 and C_5 in the ring. The above structure was further corroborated by a synthesis by Corey and Hamanka⁴. We have accomplished a facile synthesis of this hydrocarbon which is based on the application of $Ni(CO)_4$ catalysed cyclisation for the creation of a cyclic 1E,5E-diene moiety, and for the fixation of *trans* geometry of C_4 bond Claisen rearrangement of the properly substituted allyl vinyl ether has been used. Sequence of reaction is shown in Scheme 4.

3,3-Ethylenedioxybutanal (IV) was subjected to Grignard reaction with isobutylmagnesium-bromide in dry THF to afford the carbinol (V) in 76% yield. Equilibration of this alcohol with excess of ethylvinyl ether in the presence of catalytic

amount of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate provided 6,6-ethylenedioxy-2-methylhepten-2-yl vinyl ether which after chromatographic purification was subjected to pyrolysis under nitrogen atmosphere at 190-95° to get the sharp smelling aldehyde, 3,3-dimethyl-7,7-ethylenedioxy-*trans*-4-octen-1-al (VII) in 94% yield. The *trans* nature of the disubstituted double bond in the aldehyde (VII) was established by its ir absorption which showed prominent peak at 975 cm⁻¹. This aldehyde was submitted to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl α -diethylphosphonopropionate to have ethyl 9,9-ethylenedioxy-2,5,5-trimethyl-*trans*-2-*trans*-6-decadien-1-oate (VIII) as the major, higher boiling product which was deketalised with 10% HCl in acetone to yield the keto ester (IX) in 84% yield. Modified Wittig reaction with ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate in diglyme on the keto ester furnished predominantly the all *trans*-diester. However, no attempt was made to separate the all *trans*-diester from the *cis-trans* isomer because both of them would yield the product as a mixture of isomers regardless of the homogeneity of the precursors.

The conjugated diester was reduced with LAH at room temp to the corresponding diol which after conversion into the dibromide with PBr₃, was cyclised with Ni(CO)₄ in DMF to furnish humulene. The crude product was purified by column chromatography over AgNO₃ impregnated silica gel, followed by distillation under reduced pressure. The synthetic product was found to be identical (ir, pmr) with a natural sample kindly supplied by Dr. Sukh Dev.

Syntheses of elemene group of sesquiterpenes :

Some members of the elemene group of sesquiterpenes are shown below :

The salient structural features of this class are the presence of a vinylic group together with an angular methyl on the same carbonyl atom of the trisubstituted cyclohexane skeleton and two other olefinic bonds which are not in conjugation except in α -elemene.

The main difficulty in devising a clean synthesis of a particular hydrocarbon of this class is the fixation of these sensitive olefinic bonds in the desired position unambiguously and introduction of the angular methyl group.

Synthesis of β -elemene :

β -Elemene is a constituent of many essential oils, e.g. Sweetflags, Juniper, Orange and Elecampane⁷. On the basis of comprehensive chemical and spectroscopic studies the structure shown above has been assigned to β -elemene. The projected synthesis of β -elemene has been designed on the findings of Corey *et al* that the formation of a 6-membered ring relative to 8 and 10-membered ring is favoured when an acyclic terminal *bis*-allylic dihalide of the type

is cyclised with nickel carbonyl in a suitable solvent. Appropriately substituted allylic acyclic dibromide required for the synthesis of β -elemene was procured through the sequence of reactions as depicted in Scheme 5.

Scheme 5

The starting material, ethyl 2-methyl-6,6-ethylenedioxy-*trans*-2-heptenoate (I) was prepared as reported in literature. This, on reduction with LAH, afforded 2-methyl-6,6-ethylenedioxy-*trans*-2-hepten-1-ol (II) in quantitative yields. Equilibration of this allylic alcohol with excess ethylvinyl ether

VIG : SYNTHESIS OF SOME TERPENOIDS VIA NICKEL TETRACARBONYL INDUCED CYCLISATION

in presence of catalytic amount of freshly crystallised mercuric acetate provided the vinyl ether (III) in 80% yield. The Claisen rearrangement of the purified material under nitrogen atmosphere in a sealed tube at 190-195° generated as high as 82% yield of the corresponding aldehyde (IV) which was characterised through its semicarbazone derivative. The aldehyde so obtained was submitted to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl α -diethylphosphonopropionate in presence of NaH when 2-methyl-5-isopropenyl-8,8-ethylenedioxy *trans*-2-nonenate (V) was obtained in excellent yield.

This compound on deketalisation with dilute hydrochloric acid and acetone afforded ethyl 2-methyl-5-isopropenyl-8-oxo-*trans*-2-nonenate (VI). This keto-ester on being submitted to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate under the usual conditions furnished a mixture of ethyl 2,8-dimethyl-5-isopropenyl-undeca-*trans*-2-*trans*-8-diene-1,10-dioate and ethyl 2,8-dimethyl-5-isopropenyl-undeca-*trans*-2-*cis*-8-diene-1,10-dioate isomers in which the *trans*-2-*trans*-8 isomer (VII) was predominant. However, no attempt was made to separate the two isomers as both are expected to give the same final compound, β -elemene. The diester thus obtained was reduced with LAH to have the diol (VIII) as a viscous liquid which was converted into the corresponding dibromide (IX) with PBr₃ in ether. The allylic dibromide on cyclisation with nickel carbonyl according to the conditions of Corey *et al* was transformed into β -elemene (X).

The synthetic hydrocarbon, after chromatography through florosil column, showed a single spot on tlc supporting the fact that both the *trans* and *cis* allylic dibromides on cyclisation with nickel carbonyl yield the same product. The identity of the synthesised product with the natural β -elemene was established by comparison of ir and pmr spectra.

Synthesis of *dl*-bicyclo elemene :

A bicyclic sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, (-)-bicycloelemene, was isolated from peppermint oil of Bulgarian origin by Herout *et al*⁸ and also from cold pressed peel oil of Yoza by Shinoda *et al*⁹. The following structure was assigned to it on the basis of comprehensive chemical and spectral studies :

Using the nickel carbonyl induced cyclisation of the appropriate *bis*-allyl dibromide, a racemate of bicycloelemene has been synthesised.

The starting material *cis*-(*dl*)-1,1-dimethyl-2-(3'-oxobutyl) cyclopropane-3-carboxylic acid (I) was procured through condensation of methyl heptenone with ethyl diazoacetate in the presence of CuSO₄. It was esterified and then ketalised to

II, R = COOH
III, R = COOC₂H₅

IV, R = COOC₂H₅
V, R = CH₂OH
VI, R = CHO
VII, R =

VIII

IX, R = COOC₂H₅
X, R = CH₂OH
XI, R = CH₂Br

Scheme 6

give the ketal ester (III) in 80% yield. Reduction with LAH in dry ether furnishes the corresponding carbinol (V) which on oxidation with Collin's reagent gave the ketal aldehyde (VI). Modified Wittig reaction of ethyl α -diethylphosphonopropionate on the ketal aldehyde gave a stereoisomeric mixture of the esters in which the *trans* isomers predominated. The higher boiling *trans*-ketal ester on deketalisation with PTS in acetone provided the keto-ester which on submission to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate furnished the diester as a stereoisomeric mixture containing mainly the *trans*, *trans* isomer. However, no attempt was made to separate the all *trans*-isomer because the stereochemistry of the double bonds in the starting *bis*-allylic halides does not affect the composition of the isomers in the cyclised product in the Ni(CO)₄ induced coupling reaction.

This diester upon LAH reduction produced the diol as a viscous liquid which was transformed into the corresponding dibromide and subsequently subjected to nickel carbonyl induced cyclisation according to the conditions of Corey to furnish (*dl*)-bicycloelemene.

The chromatographed (silica gel) synthetic product was characterised through the comparison of its ir, pmr with that of the authentic sample kindly supplied by Dr. K. Nishimura. GLC analysis of the synthesised product also showed it to be a pure material.

Synthesis of β -elemene and elemol :

Elemol is a constituent of Manila elemi oil¹⁰ and Java citronella oil. On the basis of chemical

reactions and spectral data elemol has been assigned the structure shown below :

ELEMOL

This structure has been confirmed by Corey *et al* through a synthesis. Making use of the $\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_4$ cyclisation reaction we have also accomplished synthesis of elemol and β -elemene from the common intermediate. Scheme of reactions is shown in Scheme 7.

Scheme 7

The starting compound, 1-, methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl)cyclohexane-1, 2-diol (II) was prepared by the alkaline KMnO_4 oxidation of 1-methyl-4(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl)-1-cyclohexane (I) in 30% yield. This diol upon oxidation with lead tetraacetate in dry benzene provided the keto diester (III) which was subjected to selected Wittig reaction with α -ethoxy carbonyl ethylidene-triphenylphosphorane in refluxing benzene to yield 8-carbomethoxy-5(1',1'-ethylenedioxyethyl) non-*trans*-7-ene-2-one (IV) in 70% yield. In view of the fact that the reaction of the phosphonate carbanion with aldehydes yields only *trans* isomer, this compound was given the *trans* olefin configuration. This keto ester was submitted to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl diethylphosphoneacetate using diglyme as solvent and sodium hydride as a base to furnish the diester (V) as a mixture of (E,E) and (E,Z)

isomers. However, no attempt was made to separate the all *trans*-isomer from the *trans, cis*-isomer, because of the observed non-stereospecificity of nickel carbonyl cyclisation reaction on the nature of the double bonds in the starting allylic halides. The unsaturated diester (V) was smoothly reduced with LAH in dry ether at low temp to the diol (VI). The diol was converted into corresponding dibromide (VII) with PBr_3 in the presence of a little pyridine. The compound got deketalised during the formation of dibromide. This was indicated by the ir adsorption peak at 1710 cm^{-1} . As the presence of carbonyl group in the *bis*-allyl bromide does not interfere with the reaction of organo-nickel complexes, this keto dibromide was subjected as such to the nickel carbonyl induced cyclisation. Three spots in tlc analysis (pet. ether $4:1$) indicated the presence of three components in the cyclised product. The most polar *trans* component (R_f 0.03) was separated through column chromatography (AgNO_3 impregnated silica gel) and was subjected to the well known Wittig reaction with methylene triphenylphosphorane to furnish β -elemene. The identity of the hydrocarbon was established through comparison of its ir and nmr spectra.

The intermediate, *trans*-ketone was subjected to Grignard reaction with methylmagnesium iodide to afford the *tert*-carbinol, elemol, whose identity was also established through its ir and pmr spectra.

Synthesis of (\pm)-gejerone

Gejerone has been isolated from the essential oil of *Juniperus communis* Linn. by Thomas. On the basis of chemical as well as spectral evidence its constitution was established as 3-isopropenyl-4-methyl-4-vinylcyclohexanone. We have been able to synthesise this ketone through the use of nickel-carbonyl induced cyclisation.

Scheme 8

VIG : SYNTHESIS OF SOME TERPENOID VIA NICKEL TETRACARBONYL INDUCED CYCLISATION

The starting material, 4, 4-ethylenedioxy-1-methyl-1-cyclohexene (II), was prepared in 85% yield by ketalisation of 4-methylcyclohexen-3-one (I). This was subjected to alkaline KMnO_4 oxidation to yield the diol (III), which on oxidation with lead tetracetate in dry benzene gave the aldehyde (IV). Selective Wittig reaction of α -ethoxycarbonyl ethylidene triphenyl phosphorane on the keto aldehyde in refluxing dry benzene yielded 5,5'-(ethylene-dioxy)-8-carbomethoxy-8-methyl-7(E)-nonen-2-one (V) in 70% yield. This *trans*-keto ester was submitted to Horner Wittig reaction with ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate in diglyme to furnish the diester (VI) which was smoothly reduced to diol (VII) with LAH, converted into dibromide (VIII) with PBr_3 /ether and finally cyclised with nickel tetracarbonyl according to Corey's conditions to get geigerone (X). It is formed through Cope rearrangement of the intermediate pregeigerone, formed during the nickel carbonyl cyclisation. The synthetic hydrocarbon was purified by chromatography over silica gel column, eluting with pet. ether (40-60°) containing 10% ether. It was characterised through comparison of its ir and nmr spectra with that of an authentic sample.

Synthesis of δ -elemene :

δ -Elemene, a monocyclic sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, was isolated by Hildebrand and Sutherland from the wood oil of *Dysoxylon frazerianum* which is a commercial timber in Queensland¹¹. Later on, the same hydrocarbon was isolated from a gurjum balsam from Chittagong (Bangladesh) by Sutherland *et al.* The structure was assigned to this hydrocarbon on the basis of detailed study of its chemical behaviour and spectral data.

Using the nickel tetracarbonyl induced cyclisation we have tried to effect a synthesis of δ -elemene with the reaction sequence shown in Scheme 9.

Scheme 9

2, Methyl, 6, 6-ethylenedioxy-2-heptene (I) on hydroboration/oxidation reaction provided 6, 6-ethylenedioxy-2-methyl-hept-3-ol (II) in 75% yield. This alcohol was smoothly oxidised with Collins reagent to give the corresponding ketal ketone (III) which was subsequently submitted to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate and sodium hydride in diglyme as solvent to afford ethyl 6, 6-ethylenedioxy-3-isopropylhept-2-enoate (IV). Reduction of this ketal ester with LAH gave 6, 6-ethylenedioxy-3-isopropylhept-2-enol (V) which was again oxidised with Collins reagent to afford the aldehyde (VI) in 80% yield. The ketal aldehyde thus obtained was further submitted to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl α -diethylphosphono-propionate and the resulting ketal-ester (VII) was deprotected with dil. HCl in acetone to have ethyl 8-oxo-2-methyl-5-isopropyl-non-2, 4-dienoate (VIII) in 85% yield. This keto-ester was again submitted to modified Wittig reaction with ethyl diethylphosphonoacetate to get the diester (IX) which was as usual reduced to diol (X), converted into allylic dibromide (XI) and cyclised through reaction with $\text{Ni}(\text{CO})_4$ in DMF. An interesting observation was made when we proceeded to isolate the final expected δ -elemene. In the pmr spectrum of the synthetic sample, there appeared two sharp signals instead of one as expected, at 8.3 and 8.4 δ , suggesting thereby that there were two types of allylic methyl groups present. This prompted us to think that our synthetic sample could be a mixture of δ -elemene and a small amount of its isomeric compound. The formation of these could be visualised because, theoretically, the 10-membered cyclic intermediate is a 1, 5-diene which could cleave in two possible ways through Cope's rearrangement (cf. Scheme 9) and hence could yield a mixture of two products.

The gic analysis showed the synthetic sample to be a mixture of two compounds, almost in equal proportions. However, the work is still in progress whereby we wish to separate the two components and establish their individual identity.

References

1. E. J. COREY and M. F. SEMMELHACK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2755.
2. E. J. COREY and E. HAMANAKA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 1641.
3. E. J. COREY and E. K. W. WAT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2757.

J. INDIAN CHEM. SOC., VOL. LIX, MAY 1982

4. E. J. COREY and E. HAMANAKA, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 2758.
5. G. D. PRESTWICH, D. F. WIEMER, J. MEINWALD and J. Clardy, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 2560.
6. SUKH DEV, *Curr. Sci.*, 1951, **20**, 296.
7. G. L. K. HUNTER and J. L. PARKS, *J. Food Chem.*, 1964, **29**, 25
8. V. HEROUT, I. OGNANOV and R. VLAHOV, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1967, **32**, 808.
9. N. SHINODA, M. SHIGA and K. NISHIMURA, *Agr. Biol. Chem.*, 1970, **34**, 234.
10. A. M. CLOVER, *Philippine J. Sci.*, 1970, **2A**.
11. R. P. HILDEBRAND and M. D. SUTHERLAND, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1959, **12**, 684.